

AI as an "Object"

A critique of Graham Harman's ideas on the AI

Mohammad Hadi Forouzesh Nia

During a recent virtual lecture curated by my friend Erfan Ghiasi¹, Graham Harman—the American philosopher widely known for his Object-Oriented Ontology (OOO)—talked about his ideas surrounding AI. As one viewing the lecture, a number of points made by Harman raised questions in my mind. Although I asked them, I did not find Harman's responses satisfying enough and thus I decided to conceptualize my own position on how to understand AI in terms of OOO. This short article is my attempt towards this destination.

1. Harman and the question of AI

In his lecture, Graham Harman explicated his opinion concerning the question, 'what is AI according to OOO?' Focusing more on recent innovations in the field, he talked about how AI-based tools such as ChatGPT and Midjourney are literalizing tools. What Harman means by this is the fact that these tools do nothing more than translate the user's prompt into a literal form such as one see via image-to-text (or vice versa), or simply present the user with already existing knowledge. What Harman is opposed to is not simply the problem of 'doxa'—the claim that AI is not able to think 'outside the box' and is, instead, merely a collection of already existing opinions—rather, he is more concerned with a duality between aesthetics and literal (or direct) knowledge. For Harman, direct knowledge is always a form of what he calls reductionism, his umbrella term for a variety of philosophies which reduce the object at hand to either its parts, direct knowledge about the object, the social context of the object, etc. Opposing the literalization of objects, Harman, in *Weird Realism: Lovecraft and Philosophy*, defends H.P. Lovecraft against Edmund Wilson, the famous American literary critic, precisely because of Lovecraft's alleged 'gift,' his ability to resist all forms of literalization. As Harman says of Lovecraft,

No other writer gives us monsters and cities so difficult to describe that he can only hint at their anomalies. Not even Poe gives us such hesitant narrators, wavering so uncertainly as to whether their coming words can do justice to the unspeakable reality they confront.²

And it is not only about Lovecraft; Harman's opposition to every form of reducing objects is arguably his most fundamental idea. Following Whitehead's famous concept of 'aesthetics as first philosophy,' Harman moves towards aesthetics as a way of bypassing the obstruction of reductionism abundantly found in science and some branches of philosophy. According to him, the indirect approach exemplified by metaphors and allusions such as one finds in fictions and artworks is in a better position to say something about objects since these mediums—unlike science and most of philosophy—do not try to reduce objects to direct and descriptive knowledge about them. The allusion and the act of indirect pointing at objects found in art is translated into an ontological act of acceptance regarding the ultimate 'withdrawal' of objects from any direct access..

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FL6ChtPrVm4>

² *Weird Realism: Lovecraft and Philosophy*. Winchester, UK, Zero Books, 2012. Pg. 9–10.

Critiquing AI for its supposed literal reductionism, Harman then continues by speaking about how an aesthetic approach to objects is both essential to intelligence as such while also being unique to humans:

I think intelligence probably has something more to do with aesthetic awareness—the ability to realize that things are not literal; things are not simply reducible to bundles of qualities. This is where I see the human intelligence coming in and that it's still going to be there.[63:08-63:26]

And he adds later in the lecture:

Ultimately what we [humans] are left with is the spectatorship, the curatorship. What we're left with is the enjoyment. [80:57-90:03]

2. Is AI an object?

The question of intelligence and its relation to objects is one of the oldest questions in philosophy. Traditionally, philosophers have answered this question in two fundamental ways:

- a. All objects are intelligent (the position supported by Panpsychists such as Leibnitz and Whitehead).
- b. Some objects are intelligent (the position arguably supported by Heidegger in the mainstream interpretation of 'Dasein,' and Harman—at least in this lecture).

To examine the question of the intelligence of AI (generally speaking), we should first see if AI could really be considered an 'object' in the sense that OOO defines it. Then, more importantly, we should ask if the criterion that Harman draws for intelligence—namely the capacity for aesthetics and indirect allusion—is really something AI is incapable of. In other words, are we able to distinguish human intelligence from AI (and maybe other forms of intelligence as well) based on the capacity for aesthetic experience?

In order to address the first point, we must explore the literature of OOO to see what the criteria are for objecthood. Let us start by looking at one of the principal OOO texts in which Harman, in a style reminiscent of Leibnitz's *Monadology*³, defines what he means by OOO in 76 short theses. In the first thesis, an object is defined as follows:

An object is any unified entity, whether it has reality in the world or only in the mind. Philosophy must be broad enough to deal with both types of objects.⁴

According to this minimum criterion, an AI tool counts as an object. Furthermore, second-generation thinkers of the OOO circle pay even more attention to non-physical and widely distributed objects such as the Internet. By way of an example, Timothy Morton's concept of a hyperobject is noteworthy here:

³ *Monadology.*" Philosophical Essays. By G.W. Leibniz, Hackett Publishing Company, 1989, pp. 213-225.

⁴ Harman, Graham. *Bells and Whistles: More Speculative Realism.* Winchester, U.K.; Washington U.S.A, Zero Books, 2013. Pg. 60

Today, in the era of globalization, and what has come to be called the Anthropocene, our lives are increasingly intertwined with, and dependent upon, complex, widely distributed technical systems and networks. These mega-entities are what Timothy Morton calls *hyperobjects*. Such things are altogether real, but they are so "massively distributed in time and space" that we cannot ever see them as wholes, or grasp them all at once. Morton cites "global warming" and "nuclear radiation from plutonium" as examples of hyperobjects; one might equally well mention the internet, and the global derivatives market.⁵

Now that AI has been shown to be an object (or hyperobject) as per OOO, the second question arises: is this object 'really' intelligent? In other words, is AI capable of aesthetic experience?⁶

3. Aesthetics and objects

Let us now see what the criteria for aesthetic experience are, as per OOO. Returning once again to Harman's "Seventy-Six Theses on Object-Oriented Philosophy," we can trace a brief definition of aesthetics from the 66th thesis onward. In order to limit the length of the current article, I shall refrain from quoting all of the theses and limit myself to a short summary. For Harman, allusion is a way of pointing at some object without actually being able to fully grasp it. As he puts it in the 69th thesis: "The fascination of beauty in all its forms is that of some deeper animating principle beyond any particular visible features."⁷ He then moves on to mention some "beautiful" surprises one might find—for example, encountering "some unexpected lively principle in a book, person, or city from which we had expected only serviceable mediocrity."⁸ In the 72nd thesis, he continues: "This happens in artworks as well, though we cannot identify artworks with the form of allure known as 'beauty.' Sunsets, bird plumage, and seductive voices are beautiful without being artworks."⁹ Harman then tries to show how some creations—Duchamp's bicycle wheel is his example—may not be considered beautiful yet, nevertheless, are considered to be works of art (or vice versa—the status of an entity as a work of art may be stripped, but not on the basis of a lack of beauty). Continuing on this theme, he writes about how "this strife must be a special case in the world, or everything would be an artwork". Here 'strife' is a concept borrowed from Heideggerian aesthetics. In "The Origin of the Work of Art"¹ he takes artwork to be located at a point of tension between 'world' and 'earth' where earth provides the crude material aspects of the artwork and the world is the shared reality of human existence—the sphere of meaning where the artwork acquires significance and reveals a truth. Finally, his last thesis is as follows: "What we need to discover is how strife differs from normal

⁵ Shaviri, Steven. *Discognition*. London, Repeater Books, 2016.

⁶ As an OOO supporter myself, I do not argue against this latter proposition; namely, that intelligence has something to do with the capability for aesthetic experience. I do however reject the idea that intelligence is an all-or-nothing quality. Rather, I argue for a continuum of intelligence very similar to the Leibnizian path of thinking.

P. 69^v
Thesis 71, pg. 70.[^]
pg. 70[^]

¹ Stulberg, Robert B. "Heidegger and the Origin of the Work of Art: An Explication." *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, vol. 32, no. 2, 1973, p. 257, <https://doi.org/10.2307/429043>.

situations, and how the strife in the artwork differs from that of the broken hammer, courage, and so forth."¹

It is interesting how Harman's text ends here and his discovery remains to be finished, something he tries to do in his later works, notably in *Art and Objects*.¹ Regardless of how successful he is in his attempt, his theses offer an alternative way of looking at the question of aesthetics; one that is of course rejected by Harman according to his argument in which he claims intelligence to be a uniquely human quality.

In order to understand my alternative interpretation of Harman's theses, first let us see how he depicts the relationship between objects. Here, I quote the 4th and 5th theses:

4. What we encounter is not reality itself. Our perception of things and our practical handling of them does not exhaust the reality of things; each thing is an inexhaustible surplus.
5. This is not some quirk of the human or animal mind. Inanimate objects also fail to exhaust each other. Fire burning cotton or rocks smashing windows oversimplify their victims too.¹

What we understand from the two aforementioned theses is that all objects engage in indirect and allusive relations with each other. In other words, all objects fail to relate to the core of each other and hence do not grasp or exhaust the other; instead, they simply allusively relate to each others' changing qualities. Although this is also the account Harman gives of aesthetic experience—a relation with the surface qualities of a piece of artwork as it alludes to an unknown, underlying essence—he still argues that "while many regions of the cosmos have no need for human participation to be what they are – the motion of planets and subatomic particles comes to mind – art, like ethics, is a place where humans are a necessary part of the mix."¹ But if planets and subatomic particles interact in the same way that humans and artworks do, why should interactions between the former not qualify as genuine aesthetic experiences. It is interesting that even when writing about the interactions between objects, Harman uses the language of art and argues that "fire only encounters a caricature of cotton."¹ So, if contrary to Harman we take this 'strife' not to be a special case in the world (accessible only to humans) but an ontological foundation of it, we must concede that everything could be an artwork, and Duchamp's bicycle wheel shows that clearly. In other words, Harman borrows the Heideggerian concept of strife and changes it in a way such that it is no longer about a tension between earth and world for the human artist, but a tension between objects and their changing qualities. Although this is one step towards a more universal and less anthropocentric concept of aesthetics, such a move still retains the position of the human artist as the 'spectator' of this tension. Here, a second step remains that apparently Harman is unwilling to take: granting all objects the capability of acting as a spectator of this universal strife.

Furthermore, if we are to remain faithful to Whitehead's 'aesthetics as first philosophy,' then we cannot rather spontaneously assign this aesthetic character only to a tiny portion of the world (namely humans) but must concede that all relations between all objects have an aesthetic aspect to them—and that is what I believe to be

Pg. 70¹¹

¹ Harman, G. (2020). *Art and Objects*. Polity.

Pg. 61.¹⁷

¹ Harman, Graham. *Object-Oriented Ontology*. Penguin UK, 1 Mar. 2018. Pg. 99.

¹ Harman, Graham. *Bells and Whistles: More Speculative Realism*. Winchester, U.K.; Washington U.S.A, Zero Books, 2013. Pg. 62.

implicit in some of Harman's texts (in the aforementioned mentioned theses, for example).

This position arguably fits better with OOO as a whole since there is no longer a humanistic monopoly on aesthetic experience. If we accept the position I've just set forth, then it follows that AI as an object is also capable of aesthetic experience and since, as per Harman, this capability is taken to be essential to intelligence, then we can state that AI is in fact an intelligence. AI as an object interacts with other objects only on the surface and is never able to provide direct knowledge about them, but this is not because AI is not intelligent enough. Rather, if we accept the withdrawal of all objects from each other—Harman's key contention—then it follows that direct, exhaustive knowledge is impossible in the first place.

Of course, this alternative reading brings us closer to the Panpsychist camp, but that is the inevitable price we must pay if we want to keep our fidelity to OOO while also bypassing contradictions we have found in our path. Here, instead of having a unique capability granted to humans alone, we can speak about a continuum of intelligence varying in degrees but still standing as an underlying principle of the world.